

**NEW SUBSPECIES OF *BRACHYTA INTERROGATIONIS*
(LINNAEUS, 1758) FROM CAUCASUS
(COLEOPTERA: CERAMBYCIDAE)**

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[Lazarev, M. A. 2011. New subspecies of *Brachyta interrogationis* (Linnaeus, 1758) from Caucasus (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). Munis Entomology & Zoology, 6 (2): 859-865]

ABSTRACT: Three new subspecies are described: *Brachyta interrogationis shapsugorum* ssp. n. from the environs of Podkhrebtovoe of Krasnodar Region; *B. interrogationis miroshnikovi* ssp. n. from Lagonaki Plateau in Adygeya Republic, Karachaevo-Cherkessiya and Georgia; *B. interrogationis lederi* ssp. n. from Dagestan. Each subspecies is characterized by pronotal sculpture and character of elytral design.

KEY WORDS: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, *Brachyta*, new subspecies, Russia, Georgia.

Cerambycidae fauna of Caucasus with Transcaucasia is still very poorly investigated. The current publication continues my regular study of Caucasian Cerambycidae species by species (Lazarev, 2009a, 2009b, 2010a, 2010b, 2010c).

Up to now the taxonomy of many big groups rest uncertain. Very doubtful is the genera structure in the tribe Phytoeciini Mulsant, 1839, number of subgenera in *Xylotrechus* Chevrolat, 1860 and *Stictoleptura* Casey, 1924, the species or subspecies relations in genus *Agapanthia* Audinet-Serville, 1835 inside several groups of species: “dahli-group”, “subchalybaea-group”, “violacea-group”, “cardui-group”, as well as subspecies composition in *Brachyta caucasica* Rost, 1892, *Cortodera alpina* (Ménétriés, 1832), *C. colchica* Reitter, 1890, *Stictoleptura tonsa* (K. Daniel & J. Daniel, 1891), *Clytus arietis* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Dorcadion sulcipenne* Küster, 1847 and *D. cinerarium* Fabricius, 1787.

Caucasian populations of *Brachyta interrogationis* (Linnaeus, 1758) are strongly distant and totally isolated from the main area of the species. *B. interrogationis* does not have continuous area in Caucasus, but represented by three isolated populations and each more or less peculiar morphologically. The species is very rare in Caucasus and represented in collections by very few number of specimens, but available materials are enough to accept each known population as a distinct subspecies on the base of elytral design and pronotal sculpture.

B. interrogationis (distributed all along Eurasia from the Atlantic to the Pacific), is characterized by great number of individual variability inside each population. All Caucasian populations seem to be (as far as it is known) are contrary rather stable, each with special configuration of elytral spots, besides all Caucasian specimens have elongated prothorax, relatively longer than in European populations.

Only populations from European Russia (from Polar area to Rostov Region) are used here for representation of the nominative subspecies, as the more close geographically for Caucasian taxa. The subspecies structure of Siberian and Kazakhstan populations is very complicated and needs special study.

Several abbreviations are used in the text:

ZMM – Zoological Museum of Moscow University

MA – collection of A. I. Miroshnikov (Krasnodar)

ML – collection of M. A. Lazarev (Moscow)

***Brachyta interrogationis shapsugorum* ssp. n.**

(Fig. 1)

Type locality. Glades above the forest areas near Podkhrebtovoe (about 44°23'N, 38°59'E) in Krasnodar Region – according to the label of the holotype.

Description. Only one male known. Antennae black with a little lightened bases of 3-5th joints. Prothorax with deep anterior and posterior constrictions covered by yellowish pubescence. Pronotum convex, with dense punctation; the distance between dots always less than diameter of each. Dense long dorsal pubescence consists mostly of recumbent setae. Short and narrow glabrous line without punctation. Scutellum triangular, a little transverse, with indistinct grayish pubescence. Elytra yellow with black spots, just a little tapering posteriorly. Elytral suture and epipleurae totally yellow. Each elytron with 6 black spots: two big discal spots, scutellar spot, small humeral, lateral and apical spots. A pair of scutellar spots form with a black scutellum a narrow transverse stripe at elytral base. A narrow yellow line is hardly visible along scutellum borders. Anterior big discal spots with sharpened apices obliquely attenuated. Posterior big discal subround spots reaching epipleurae. Small humeral spots elongated. Small lateral spots triangular not reaching epipleurae. Apical spots rounded, joined with big posterior discal spot by narrow lateral line above epipleurae. Legs black with yellowish bases of all tibiae. Pygidium and postpygidium with small emarginations.

Body length 14.0 mm; width 4.7 mm.

Distribution. Only one locality known - glade above the forest areas near Podkhrebtovoe (about 44°23'N, 38°59'E) in Krasnodar Region.

Differential diagnosis. New subspecies differs from *B. i. miroshnikovi* ssp. n. and *B. i. lederi* ssp. n. by slightly lightened bases of 3rd-5th antennal joints and lightened tibiae, small and conjugated pronotal punctation, smooth pronotal line, totally yellow epipleurae and elytral suture, elytral design.

Material. Holotype: male, “Krasnodar Region, Tuapse District, NNE Podkhrebtovoe env., 44°23'47.40"N, 38°59'19.57" E, 19-27.VI.2006 leg. I.Melnik” – ML.

Etymology. Shapsugs are a self-designation of people/tribe of the Adyghe branch, who are currently living in Tuapse and Sochi districts of Krasnodar Region and in the Republic of Adygea in Russia.

***Brachyta interrogationis miroshnikovi* ssp. n.**

(Figs. 2-6)

Evodinus (s.str.) *interrogationis*, Plavilstshikov, 1936: 198 (Caucasus, Elbrus env., Teberda), part.

Brachyta interrogationis, Miroshnikov, 1990: 27 (Elbrus, Teberda, Arkhyz env., Georgia: Omalo), part.

Type locality. Abadzekh Mt. (2000-2100 m above the level of the sea) at Lagonaki Plateau in Adygeya.

Description. Antennae totally black. Anterior and posterior prothoracic constrictions relatively shallow, without dense setae stripes. Pronotum convex, with dense punctation; the distance between central dots often longer than

diameter of each. Long dorsal pubescence consists of dense recumbent setae and numerous erect setae. Glabrous area in the middle of pronotum relatively wide, partly punctated. Scutellum elongated, rounded apically with dense pubescence. Elytra yellow with black spots, strongly tapering posteriorly in males and hardly tapering in females. Elytral suture with narrow black line. Epipleurae always yellow anteriorly and black apically. In specimens from Teberda epipleurae black only near apices. In specimens from Georgia and Adygeya epipleurae can be black to about humeri. Each elytron with a big black "C"- shaped spot, typical for the species, and with 4 small spots: scutellar, humeral, lateral and apical. A pair of scutellar spots form with a black scutellum a transverse stripe of different width with irregular posterior margin, which is often much wider than scutellum. A narrow yellow line along scutellum borders never visible. "C"- shaped spot can be fused with scutellar spots in Teberda specimens and always reaching epipleurae posteriorly. Humeral spots strongly elongated and fused with black epipleurae if epipleurae are black anteriorly. Lateral spots usually not touching epipleurae also if they are black, but sometimes fused with epipleural line. Apical spots always joined with "C"- shaped spot, sometimes rather wide including black epipleurae. Legs totally black. Pygidium and postpygidium with small emarginations.

Body length in males: 11.5-13.2 mm, in females: 13.0-14.8 mm; body width in males: 4.0-4.7 mm, in females: 4.8-5.2 mm.

Distribution. The subspecies is represented by at least 5 strongly distant populations. The type population is registered on Abadzesh Mt. (2000-2100 m) at Lagonaki Plateau in Adygeya. A population from Teberda was already known to Plavilstshikov (1936). Another population was discovered by V. Dolin in Georgia (Miroshnikov, 1990) – Omalo environs (1800m). Besides the taxon was recorded from Elbrus (Plavilstshikov, 1936) and Arkhyz (Miroshnikov, 1990).

Differential diagnosis. New subspecies differs from *B. i. shapsugorum* ssp. n. by totally black antennae and tibiae, big pronotal punctation, smooth pronotal line partly punctated laterally, black elytral suture, partly black epipleurae and elytral design. It differs from *B. i. lederi* ssp. n. by elytral design and convex pronotum.

Material. Holotype: male, "Adygeya, Lagonaki Plateau, Abadzesh Mountain, 2000-2100 m, 13.07.2004, A.Miroshnikov" – AM; 10 Paratypus: 1 female with same label – AM; 3 males, 3 females, Georgia, Omalo, 1800 m., 25.06.1988, V.Dolin – AM; 1 male, 1 female, Teberda, P.Elagin – ZMM; 1 female, Teberda, Erkhi canyon, 21.VI., A.Zolotarev – ZMM.

Etymology. The new subspecies is dedicated to a well known specialist on fauna, taxonomy and biology of Palaearctic Cerambycidae - Alexandr Ivanovitch Miroshnikov.

***Brachyta interrogationis lederi* ssp. n.**

(Fig. 7)

Evodinus interrogationis, König, 1899: 394 (Dagt.), part.

Evodinus (s.str.) *interrogationis*, Plavilstshikov, 1915: 370 (Dagestan), part.

Brachyta interrogationis, Miroshnikov, 1990: 27 (Dagestan), part; 2004: 134 (Dagestan), part.

Type locality. Dagestan – according to the label of the holotype.

Description. Only one female known. Antennae totally black. Anterior and posterior prothoracic constrictions shallow without dense hair stripes. Pronotum moderately flat, with dense punctation. Dense dorsal erect pubescence relatively short. Glabrous pronotal line short and narrow, but laterally punctated. Scutellum elongated, rounded apically with dense grayish pubescence. Elytra yellow with black spots, just a little tapering posteriorly. Elytral suture with very narrow black line. Epipleurae yellow anteriorly and black posteriorly. Each elytron with 6 black spots: two big discal spots, scutellar spot, small humeral, lateral and apical spots. A pair of scutellar spots form with a black scutellum a very narrow transverse stripe at elytral base, which is about two times shorter than scutellum. A narrow yellow line between scutellum and scutellar black spots not visible. Anterior discal spots narrow elongated sharpened anteriorly and posteriorly. Posterior discal spots obliquely-transverse, reaching epipleurae. Humeral spots elongated. Small lateral spots oval not reaching epipleurae. Apical spots rounded, joined with big posterior discal spot by narrow lateral line above epipleurae. Legs black with hardly yellowish bases of all tibiae. Pygidium and postpygidium with small emarginations.

Body length 12.4 mm; width - 4.0 mm.

Distribution. Known from Dagestan mountain area.

Differential diagnosis. New subspecies differs from *B. i. shapsugorum* ssp. n. by totally black antennae and tibiae, black elytral suture, smooth pronotal line partly punctated laterally, partly black epipleurae. It differs from *B. i. shapsugorum* ssp. n. and *B. i. miroshnikovi* ssp. n. by the character of pronotal punctation and elytral design.

Material. Holotype: female, "Dagestan Leder. Reitter." – ZMM.

Etymology. The new taxon is dedicated to a great European insect collector Hans Leder, who collected holotype.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author is very grateful to A. A. Gusakov and A. L. Ozerov (Zoological Museum of Moscow University), A. I. Miroshnikov (Krasnodar) for providing with the materials for study.

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Figure 1. *Brachyta interrogationis shapsugorum* **ssp. n.**: Holotype, male, Krasnodar Region, Tuapse District, NNE Podkhrebtovoe env., 44°23'47.40"N, 38°59'19.57"E.

Figure 2-4. *Brachyta interrogationis miroschnikovi* **ssp. n.**: 2. Holotype, male, Adygeya, Lagonaki Plateau, Abadzesh Mountain, 2000-2100 m; 3-4. Paratypus, male, female, Georgia, Omalo, 1800 m.

Figure 5-6. *Brachyta interrogationis miroshnikovi* **ssp. n.**: Paratypus, male, female, Teberda.

Figure 7. *Brachyta interrogationis lederi* **ssp. n.**: Holotype, female, Dagestan.